

Tournament of Ten

Yichen Ding, Vania Gautam, and Yasma Esteitieh
Counselor: Dhruv Bhatia
Mentors: Nathan Kaplan, David Fried, and John Sim

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1 Introduction

In 2009, the game show *Who Wants to be a Millionaire* created an event called the *Tournament of Ten* where players from the first half of the season were asked to return and compete for a \$1,000,000 prize. Since the Tournament of Ten was a continuation of a previous game, all participants entered the game with the amount of money they won from previous rounds. We call this amount the starting money for each participant. All of the participants were ranked based on their starting money where the player ranked 10th had the lowest starting money and player ranked 1st had the highest starting money. In the event of a tie, total time was used as a tie breaker. During the tournament, each participant was presented with a different question. The participants with the least amount of starting money answered questions first. Hence, participant 10 went first and participant 1 was the last person to answer. If a player was to answer their question incorrectly, they would leave with only \$25,000. At the end of the tournament, out of all players who answered correctly, the highest ranked one won \$1,000,000. If a participant answered correctly but was not the highest ranked player to answer correctly, then they would leave the game with their original starting money. A participant could also choose not to answer their question and leave with their original starting money.

One might wonder what the strategy for a player ranked near the bottom should be to maximize expected profits. In this paper we explore some of the mathematics behind this Tournament.

2 Tournament of Three

We begin by examining a simpler version of this Tournament: The Tournament of Three.

To mathematically model the tournament, we make a few simplifying assumptions.

- Questions asked are drawn from a discrete probability distribution with three types of questions that have an equal chance of being asked. The three types of questions are divided based on their "easiness" into the categories *easy*, *medium*, and *hard*. Any participant has a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance of guessing correctly on an easy question, a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance of guessing correctly on a medium question, and $\frac{1}{4}$ chance of guessing correctly on a hard question.
- When a participant receives a question, they know its corresponding "easiness."
- A participant will always guess when their expected profit is greater than zero.

Additionally, we note that the behavior of a player is independent of all previous players who have gone. This is because the number of previous players who have answered their questions, regardless of answering correct or incorrect, should have no effect on the question that a player receives or on the probability that a higher ranking player will answer their question correctly. This is a useful fact as it is often easier to perform calculations in reverse order and examine the highest ranked player first, even though they are the last to receive their question.

We consider a tournament with three players named JSD, KG, and JB with rank and starting money given by the following table.

Rank	Contestant	Starting Money (\$ in thousands)
1	JSD	250
2	KG	100
3	JB	100

Since it is easier to work backwards, we first observe what happens when JSD is asked a question. If JSD is asked an easy question, JSD's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{3}{4} \cdot 1000 + \frac{1}{4} \cdot 25 - 250 = 506.25$$

This is because there is a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance of answering an easy question right and winning 1000, and a $\frac{1}{4}$ chance of answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. We subtract JSD's starting money because we are measuring expected *profit*. Since 506.25 is greater than zero, JSD will guess.

If JSD is asked a medium question, JSD's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot 1000 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 25 - 250 = 262.5$$

This is because there is a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance of answering a medium question right and winning 1000 and a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance of answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. Since 262.5 is greater than zero, JSD will guess.

If JSD is asked a hard question, JSD's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{1}{4} \cdot 1000 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 25 - 250 = 18.75$$

This is because there is a $\frac{1}{4}$ chance of answering a hard question right and winning 1000, and a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance of answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. Since 18.75 is greater than zero, JSD will guess.

Thus, JSD will guess on every type of question and JSD's overall chance of being correct is

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

We will use this value in our calculations for KG.

If KG is asked an easy question, KG's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot 1000 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 100 \right) + \frac{1}{4} \cdot 25 - 100 = 318.75$$

This is because there is a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance of KG answering an easy question right but a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance that JSD will answer his question correctly and KG only keeps her starting money, and a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance that JSD will not guess correctly and KG will win 1000. This is added to the $\frac{1}{4}$ chance of KG answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. Since 318.75 is greater than zero, KG will guess.

If KG is asked a medium question, KG's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot 1000 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 100 \right) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 25 - 100 = 187.5$$

This is because there is a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance of answering a medium question right but a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance that JSD will answer his question correctly and KG only keeps her starting money, and a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance that JSD will not guess correctly and KG will win 1000. This is added to the $\frac{1}{2}$ chance of KG answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. Since 187.5 is greater than zero, KG will guess.

If KG is asked a hard question, KG's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{1}{4}(\frac{1}{2} \cdot 1000 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 100) + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 25 - 100 = 56.25$$

This is because there is a $\frac{1}{4}$ chance of answering a hard question right but a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance that JSD will answer his question correctly and KG only keeps her starting money, and a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance that JSD will not guess correctly and KG will win 1000. This is added to the $\frac{3}{4}$ chance of KG answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. Since 56.25 is greater than zero, KG will guess.

Therefore, since KG will guess on every type of question, KG's overall chance of being correct is

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{2}$$

We will use this value in our calculations for JB. Since the overall probability of JSD being correct is $1/2$ and the overall probability of KG being correct is $1/2$, given that JB is correct, the probability that JB is the highest ranked player who is correct is $(1 - 1/2) \cdot (1 - 1/2) = 1/4$. We now proceed with our calculations for JB.

If JB was asked an easy question, JB's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{3}{4}(\frac{1}{4} \cdot 1000 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 100) + \frac{1}{4} \cdot 25 - 100 = 150$$

This is because there is a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance of JB answering an easy question right but a $\frac{1}{4}$ chance that JB is the highest ranked player to guess right wins 1000 and a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance that JB is not the highest ranked player to guess right and leaves with his starting money. This is added to the $\frac{1}{4}$ chance of answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. Since 150 is greater than zero, JB will guess.

If JB was asked a medium question, JB's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{1}{2}(\frac{1}{4} \cdot 1000 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 100) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 25 - 100 = 75$$

This is because there is a $\frac{1}{2}$ chance of answering a medium question right but a $\frac{1}{4}$ chance that JB is the highest ranked player to guess right wins 1000 and a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance that JB is not the highest ranked player to guess right and leaves with his starting money. This is added to the $\frac{1}{2}$ chance of answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25. Since 75 is greater than zero, JB will guess.

If JB was asked a hard question, JB's expected profit of guessing is

$$\frac{1}{4}(\frac{1}{4} \cdot 1000 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 100) + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 25 - 100 = 0$$

This is because there is a $\frac{1}{4}$ chance of answering a hard question right but a $\frac{1}{4}$ chance that JB is the highest ranked player to guess right wins 1000 and a $\frac{3}{4}$ chance that JB is not the highest ranked player to guess right and leaves with his starting money. This is added to the $\frac{3}{4}$ chance of answering the question wrong and leaving with just 25.

In the case that a player's expected profits is zero, we assume that the player will not guess on that question. We base this decision on the real life phenomenon that people tend to be risk-averse with gains, i.e people will usually choose a sure option over a riskier option.

Therefore, JB will only guess on easy and medium questions. Then, JB's overall chance of being correct is

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{2} = \frac{5}{12}$$

If our tournament had more players, this value would be used in calculations for lower ranked players. In terms of our Tournament of Three, we have completely described the behavior of the three players (i.e. the conditions under which each player will guess on their question).

3 A Note on Notation

As seen in the introductory example, many different values come into play when determining the behavior of players in the Tournament of Ten. We find it useful to define in this section the notation and definitions that will be used throughout the rest of the paper.

Definition 3.1. A **probability mass function** is a function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ of a *discrete* random variable X with the properties

$$f(x) = P(X = x)$$

and

$$\sum_x f(x) = 1.$$

Definition 3.2. A **probability density function** is a function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of a *continuous* random variable X with the properties

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = P(X \in [a, b])$$

and

$$\int_0^1 f(x) dx = 1.$$

Notation 3.3. P_i is the player ranked i th.

Notation 3.4. $w > 0$ is the prize money. In our introductory example, $w = 1,000,000$.

Notation 3.5. $l \geq 0$ is the money a player takes home if they guess incorrectly. In our introductory example, $l = 25,000$.

Notation 3.6. m_i is the starting money of P_i . For all i , we have $l < m_i < w$.

Notation 3.7. h_i is the probability that no P_j such that $j < i$ guessed and guessed correctly.

Notation 3.8. c_i is the probability that P_i guessed and guessed correctly.

Definition 3.9. The **easiness** of a question is the probability that a player guessing on that question will guess correctly.

Notation 3.10. $E(P_i, q)$ is the expected profit of P_i guessing on a question of easiness q .

Notation 3.11. $E'(P_i, f(x))$ is the expected profit of P_i competing in a tournament where question easiness is drawn based on the probability density function or probability mass function $f(x)$.

Notation 3.12. t_i is the **guess threshold** of P_i , i.e. the least value in the range $[0, 1]$ such that $E(P_i, t_i) \geq 0$. If no such value exists, we define $t_i = 1$.

4 Different Question Distributions

The main goal of this paper is to analyze the effect of different probability distributions for question easiness on the outcome of the Tournament of Ten. In our introductory example, we analyzed a three player game with question easiness values drawn from the set $\{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{4}\}$. We specified that each question easiness value in our set had a $\frac{1}{3}$ chance of being drawn. Thus, our probability mass function $D(x)$ for the question easiness values was

$$D(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} & x = \frac{1}{4} \\ \frac{1}{3} & x = \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{3} & x = \frac{3}{4} \\ 0 & x \notin \{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{4}\} \end{cases}$$

However, we do not have to be limited to a probability mass function where each question easiness value is equally likely to be drawn. In general, given a set $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$ of n question easiness values and a set $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ of corresponding probabilities, we can define a probability mass function

$$D(x) = \begin{cases} a_i & x = s_i \\ 0 & x \notin S \end{cases}$$

where the probability of drawing a question of easiness s_i is a_i .

Once we set a probability mass function $D(x)$ defined by S and A for a tournament, we can determine the behavior of each player (i.e. the conditions under which each player will guess). As in our introductory example, we assume that a player will guess whenever their expected profit is positive. Using the same method as the introductory example, we have

$$E(P_i, q) = qh_iw + q(1 - h_i)m_i + (1 - q)l - m_i \tag{1}$$

To find which questions P_i would guess on, we can evaluate $E(P_i, q)$ for each $q \in S$ and check for which q 's $E(P_i, q) > 0$. However, this method will become cumbersome as the size of S increases. Even with the help of a computer, this method is very inefficient. Moreover, if we wish to examine games where question easinesses are drawn from a continuous probability distribution, this method becomes unusable. We make our method more efficient and robust with the following proposition.

Proposition 4.1. *For any question easiness q ,*

$$q > t_i \Rightarrow E(P_i, q) > 0$$

Proof. Let $q > t_i$. Then, $q = t_i + k$ for some $k > 0$. From Equation 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} E(P_i, t_i) &= t_i h_i w + t_i (1 - h_i) m_i + (1 - t_i) l - m_i \\ &= t_i (h_i (w - m_i) + m_i - l) + l - m_i. \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned}
E(P_i, q) &= E(P_i, t + k) = (t_i + k)(h_i(w - m) + m_i - l) + l - m_i \\
&= k(h_i(w - m_i) + m_i - l) + t_i(h_i(w - m) + m_i - l) + l - m_i \\
&= k(h_i(w - m_i) + m_i - l) + E(P_i, t_i)
\end{aligned}$$

By definition, $w > m_i$. Thus $w - m_i > 0$. h_i is a probability, so $h_i \geq 0$. Thus $h_i(w - m_i) \geq 0$. By definition $m_i > l$, so $m_i - l > 0$. Thus $h_i(w - m) + m_i - l > 0$. We know $k > 0$ and $E(P_i, t_i) \geq 0$. So, $k(h_i(w - m_i) + m_i - l) + E(P_i, t_i) > 0$. Therefore, we have

$$E(P_i, q) > 0.$$

□

Using Proposition 4.1, we first compute t_i , the guess threshold of P_i , using the formula

$$t_i = \frac{m_i - l}{wh_i + (1 - h_i)m_i - l} \quad (2)$$

To obtain Equation 2, we solved for t_i in the equation $E(P_i, t_i) = 0$. Then, for any question easiness q , instead of checking if $E(P_i, q) > 0$ we just check if $q > t_i$. We can use this method for any discrete or continuous probability distributions as long as we can calculate t_i .

In order to calculate t_i , we need the formula for h_i . If $i = 1$, then $h_i = 1$, because no players ranked above P_1 will ever guess and guess correctly since P_1 is the highest ranked player. Otherwise, if $i > 1$, we have

$$h_i = \prod_{k=1}^{i-1} (1 - c_k) \quad (3)$$

To calculate c_i , we will model off our method in introductory example. We take each possible question easiness that P_i will guess on multiply it by the probability of drawing a question of that easiness value. Then, we sum over all the products to get c_i . For a tournament with a discrete probability mass function $D(x)$ described by the set S of question easinesses and the set A of corresponding probabilities, we have

$$c_i = \sum_{\substack{s > t_i \\ s \in S}} s \cdot D(s) \quad (4)$$

We can also extend this method to work for a continuous probability density function $Q(x)$, where we replace the sum with an integral:

$$c_i = \int_{t_i}^1 x \cdot Q(x) dx \quad (5)$$

In the above formula, $Q(x) dx$ is analogous to $D(s)$ and can be thought of as the probability of drawing a question of easiness x . x is analogous to s . While in the discrete case we summed over all $s \in S$ such that $s > t_i$, in the continuous case we integrate over all x in the interval $[t_i, 1]$.

We now have a recursive method to calculate t_i for any i and any discrete question distribution $D(x)$ or continuous question distribution $Q(x)$: calculating t_i relies on the value of h_i , which relies on the value of c_{i-1} , which relies on the value of t_{i-1} , and the cycle continues down to the base case t_1 , c_1 , and h_1 where $h_1 = 1$.

5 Maximizing Expected Profit

With the a method to calculate the guess threshold, we now have a way to predict how each player in the tournament will behave for an arbitrary probability distribution (and under the condition that players will guess on a question whenever their expected profit is positive). We will now focus on the question ”**which question easiness distributions maximize the expected profit of P_i ?**”

To begin, we will find a formula for $E'(P_i, f(x))$ which gives the expected profit for a player P_i competing in a tournament with question easiness drawn from the probability distribution $f(x)$.

For a discrete probability distribution function $D(x)$ specified by the set S of question easiness values and the set A of corresponding probabilities, we have

$$E'(P_i, D(x)) = \sum_{s \in S} \max(0, E(P_i, s)) \cdot D(s) \quad (6)$$

For each possible question easiness value $s \in S$, we evaluate the expected profit of P_i receiving an easiness s question, which is $\max(0, E(P_i, s))$, and multiply by $D(s)$, the probability of drawing a question of easiness s . Then we sum over all these values to get the expected profit.

Since we know $E(P_i, s) > 0$ whenever $s > t_i$, we can also say

$$E'(P_i, D(x)) = \sum_{\substack{s \leq t_i \\ s \in S}} 0 \cdot D(s) + \sum_{\substack{s > t_i \\ s \in S}} E(P_i, s) \cdot D(s). \quad (7)$$

Thus,

$$E'(P_i, D(x)) = \sum_{\substack{s > t_i \\ s \in S}} E(P_i, s) \cdot D(s). \quad (8)$$

Analogously, for a continuous question easiness distribution $Q(x)$, we have

$$E'(P_i, Q(x)) = \int_0^1 \max(0, E(P_i, x)) \cdot Q(x) dx. \quad (9)$$

Here, as in Equation 5, $Q(x) dx$ is analogous to $D(x)$ and can be thought of as the probability of drawing a question of easiness x . As in the discrete case, we can break the integral into two to remove the max function:

$$E'(P_i, Q(x)) = \int_0^{t_i} 0 \cdot Q(x) dx + \int_{t_i}^1 E(P_i, x) \cdot Q(x) dx. \quad (10)$$

Thus,

$$E'(P_i, Q(x)) = \int_{t_i}^1 E(P_i, x) \cdot Q(x) dx. \quad (11)$$

Now that we have a formula for $E'(P_i, f(x))$ for any probability distribution $f(x)$, we have all the tools we need to investigate which question easiness distributions maximize the expected profit of P_i .

6 Data Analysis and Visualization

To begin to examine which question distributions will maximize the expected profits of P_i , we ran simulations of tournaments with question easiness values drawn from four distributions—uniform, normal, increasing, and decreasing distributions—and assessed the effect of the different distributions on $E'(P_i, f(x))$.

The probability density function of the uniform distribution is given by

$$Q(x) = 1.$$

The probability density function for a normal distribution is given by

$$Q(x) = \frac{e^{-(x-\mu)^2/2\sigma^2}}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}}.$$

where μ is the mean and σ is the standard deviation. Since we want to draw question easiness values in the range $[0, 1]$, we set $\mu = 1/2$ to center the distribution in the range $[0, 1]$ and set $\sigma = 1/6$ to ensure, by the Empirical Rule, that 99.7% of the area under the normal curve falls within the range $[0, 1]$.

We define the probability density function of our increasing distribution to be

$$Q(x) = 2x.$$

and the probability density function of our decreasing distribution to be

$$Q(x) = -2x + 2.$$

With our four probability distributions defined, we considered the Tournament of Two with two players P_1 and P_2 with starting money m_1 and m_2 . We ran a simulation for the Tournament of Two where we defined $w = 1000$ and $l = 0$, and analyzed how the value of $E'(P_i, f(x))$ changed over different values of m_1 and m_2 for each of our four question easiness distributions. Utilizing the 3D visualization tool *Graphing Calculator 3D*, we obtained the graphs on the next page. In the graphs, m1 denotes m_1 , m2 denotes m_2 , and E2 denotes $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ for the appropriate probability distribution $Q(x)$.

Figure 1: Uniform Distribution

Figure 2: Normal Distribution

Figure 3: Increasing Distribution

Figure 4: Decreasing Distribution

We notice that in the graphs of all four distributions, the greatest value of $E(P_2, q)$ is reached when m_2 is at its least value and m_1 is at its highest value.

Proposition 6.1. *Given a probability distribution $Q(x)$, $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ is maximized when m_1 is maximized and m_2 is minimized.*

Proof. Assume that players P_1 and P_2 have starting money m_1 and m_2 .

We will first show that $E(P_2, q)$ increases as m_1 increases. From Equation 4.1, we have

$$t_1 = \frac{m_1 - l}{wh_1 + (1 - h_1)m_1 - l}$$

Additionally, we defined $h_1 = 1$, thus

$$t_1 = \frac{m_1 - l}{w - l}$$

w and l are non negative constants with $w - l > 0$. Therefore, increasing m_1 will increase t_1 .

As t_1 increases, c_1 decreases, as seen from Equation 5

$$c_1 = \int_{t_1}^1 x \cdot Q(x) dx.$$

Then, as c_1 decreases, $h_2 = \prod_{k=1}^1 (1 - c_k) = 1 - c_1$ will increase. Finally, as h_2 increases,

$$E(P_2, q) = qh_2w + q(1 - h_2)m_2 + (1 - q)l - m_2$$

also increases because $qw > qm_2$ and $1 - h_2$ decreases as h_2 increases. Thus $E(P_2, q)$ increases as m_1 increases.

We will now show that $E(P_2, q)$ increases as m_2 decreases. Again, we have

$$\begin{aligned} E(P_2, q) &= qh_2w + q(1 - h_2)m_2 + (1 - q)l - m_2 \\ &= qh_2w + (1 - q)l + m_2(q(1 - h_2) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

We have $q, h_2 \in [0, 1] \Rightarrow q(1 - h_2) \in [0, 1] \Rightarrow q(1 - h_2) - 1 \leq 0$. Thus, as m_2 decreases, $E(P_2, q)$ increases or stays constant.

Combining the two statements we proved, we conclude that $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ is maximized when m_1 is maximized and m_2 is minimized. □

Having proved a statement about $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ that is true for all the graph, we now make some observations about each individual graph.

In the graph of the uniform distribution, the greatest value reached by $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ is approximately 480. In the graph of the normal distribution, the the greatest value reached $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ is approximately 500. In the graph of the increasing distribution, the greatest value reached by $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ is approximately 650. In the graph of the decreasing distribution, the greatest value reached by $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ is approximately 330.

In the uniform distribution graph, as m_2 is held constant and m_1 decreases, $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ decreases at a relatively slow rate. This property is desirable for maximizing $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ we do not want $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ to steeply drop as m_1 decreases.

In the normal distribution graph, $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ maintains a relatively high value for values of m_1 in the approximate range $[400, 800]$ and values of m_2 in the approximate range $[1, 400]$. However,

as m_2 increases, the value of $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ exhibits a steep decrease in value, flattening to almost 0 at approximately $m_2 = 500$.

In the increasing distribution graph, $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ achieves the highest peak value out of all four distributions. However, the value of $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ decreases relatively steeply as m_2 increases and especially as m_1 decreases.

In the decreasing graph, $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ achieves the lowest peak value out of all four distributions. However, as m_2 is held constant and m_1 decreases, $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ stays relatively constant. This is a property that is desirable for maximizing $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ as we do not want $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ to steeply drop as m_1 decreases.

We will now directly compare the graphs of the distributions to each other. Below are three figures showing all graphs plotted in the same space from different angles.

Figure 5: All Distributions

Figure 6: All Distributions: top view

Figure 7: All Distributions: bottom view

From Figure 6, the top view, we can clearly see that there is no point where the decreasing distribution gives the highest $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ out of all four distributions. In fact, by looking at Figure 7, the bottom view, we observe that for the majority of values m_1 and m_2 , the decreasing distribution gives the least value for $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ out of all four distributions.

Additionally, from the bottom view we observe that the normal distribution yields the least values for $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ as m_2 increases, confirming our previous observation of the normal distribution performing suboptimally as m_2 increases. From the top view, we see that the normal distribution performs best out of all four distributions for mid range values of m_1 and low range values of m_2 , again confirming our previous observations.

Looking from the top view, we can see that roughly for roughly half of the pairs (m_1, m_2) , the increasing distribution gives the highest value of $E'(P_2, Q(x))$, especially for high values of m_1 . As m_1 decreases, the normal and uniform distributions become more optimal distributions for maximizing $E'(P_2, Q(x))$. The uniform and normal distributions each yield the highest value of $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ out of all four distributions for about one fourth of the pairs (m_1, m_2) .

Overall, out of the four distributions, the increasing distribution yields the the highest value of $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ for the most pairs (m_1, m_2) .

7 Code Overview

The number of variables and computations involved in determining the outcome of of a tournament rapidly increases as the number of players increases. Even in the case of the Tournament of Two, it was not feasible to hand calculate how $E(P_2, Q(x))$ changed with different probability density functions $Q(x)$ and different starting moneys m_1 and m_2 . Thus, coding a simulation and utilizing 3D data visualization tools was integral to our research process. In this section we provide an overview of our simulation and visualization code.

We coded our simulation in *Python* using an object oriented structure. We divided our program into two classes, the `Participant` class and the `Game` class. The `Participant` class encapsulated all the variables that were associated each P_i , while the `Game` class defined the parameters of the game and simulated the behavior of the participants.

In the `Participant` class, we included the fields `name`, `start_money`, `prob_of_correct`, `prob_no_higher_correct`, `guess_threshold`, and `expected_profit` corresponding to the name of the participant, m_i , c_i , h_i , t_i , and $E(P_i, Q(x))$ respectively. We also included the boolean fields `guess` and `correct` would be used in our simulation code to track whether a particular participant chose to guess on a question and if they answered correctly. Finally, we created the field `next_participant` which references the participant ranked one above the current participant (i.e. the next participant to receive a question after the current participant). We created the `next_participant` field with the goal of utilizing dynamic programming in mind. For each `Participant` object, we initialize the fields in the following way.

```
class Participant:
    def __init__(self, name : str, start_money : float):
        self.name = name
        self.start_money = start_money
        self.guess = False
        self.correct = False
        self.prob_of_correct = 0
        self.prob_no_higher_correct = 1
        self.guess_threshold = 1
```

```

self.expected_profit = 0
self.next_participant = None

```

Before a participant is presented with a question, we assume that the participant will not guess. Thus, we initialize `guess` and `correct` to `False`. Similarly, we initialize `prob_of_correct` to 0, `guess_threshold` to 1, and `expected_profit` to 0 because we assume that the participant will not guess. We initialized `prob_no_higher_correct` to 1 because $h_1 = 1$. For all participants not ranked first, `prob_no_higher_correct` will be calculated later in the program. Finally, we initialize `next_participant` as `None`, another field that will be assigned later in the program in the context of a game.

The `Participant` class contains one main method, `strategy`, which takes as parameters Q , the probability distribution of the question easiness values in the game the participant is competing in; w , the prize money of the game; and l , the amount of money the participant takes home if they answer a question incorrectly. Using these inputs, the `strategy` function calculates and sets the values for `prob_of_correct`, `prob_no_higher_correct`, `guess_threshold`, and `expected_profit`. We define two versions of `strategy`: one which takes as a parameter a discrete probability distribution Q and one which takes a continuous probability distribution. In this paper we will only discuss the continuous version. The discrete version is very similar and can be easily adapted from the continuous version. The `strategy` function for continuous probability distributions is defined as follows.

```

def strategy(self, Q : function, w : float, l : float):

    # calculate prob_no_higher_correct
    if self.next_participant != None:
        self.prob_no_higher_correct = self.next_participant.prob_no_higher_correct
            * (1 - self.next_participant.prob_correct)
    self.guess_threshold = (self.start_money - l)/(w*self.prob_no_higher_correct+
        (1-self.prob_no_higher_correct)*self.start_money-l)

    # calculate prob_of_correct
    self.prob_of_correct = integrate(x*Q(x), self.guess_threshold, 1)

    # calculate expected_profit
    def E(x):
        return (x*self.prob_no_higher_correct*w + x*(1-self.prob_no_higher_correct)
            *self.start_money + (1-x)*l) * Q(x)
    self.expected_profit = integrate(E, self.guess_threshold, 1)

```

The `strategy` function is for the most part a simple application of Equations 1, 2, 3, 5, and 11. When calculating `prob_no_higher_correct`, which corresponds to h_i , instead of calculating

$$h_i = \prod_{k=1}^{i-1} (1 - c_k),$$

for every participant, we use the equivalent form

$$h_i = (1 - c_{i-1}) \cdot h_{i-1}. \quad (12)$$

The values c_{i-1} and h_{i-1} are already stored in the variables `next_participant.prob_of_correct` and `next_participant.prob_no_higher_correct` respectively. Thus, we can employ dynamic programming using Equation 12 to make our program more efficient.

The `Participant` class also contains a `reset` function which sets all fields to their original initialized values. The `reset` function will be called when we simulate games multiple times.

In the `Game` class, we included the fields `participants`, a list of all participants competing in a game; `Q`, the probability density function of question easiness values; `w`, the prize money; `l`, the amount of money a participant who answers incorrectly takes home; and `icdf`, the inverse of the cumulative distribution function of question easiness values. We will need `icdf` to generate random question easiness values based on `Q`. As in the `strategy` method in the `Participant` class, we provide the code for a game with question easiness values drawn from a continuous distribution, but games with a discrete probability distribution are a simple variation.

The `Game` class contains one main method, `run`, which simulates one game. `Game` also contains the methods `add_participant`, which adds an inputted participant to `participants`; `sort_participants`, which sorts `participants` according to the starting money of each participant; and `reset`, which calls `reset` on each participant in `participants`. The `run` method is shown below.

```
def run(self):
    self.sort_participants()
    for i in range(len(self.participants)):

        # assign next_participant field
        if i != 0:
            self.participants[i].next_participant = self.participants[i-1]

        # participants play the game
        self.participants[i].strategy(self.Q, self.l, self.w)
        q = self.icdf(random.random())

        if self.participants[i].guess_threshold <= q:
            self.participants[i].guess = True
            self.participants[i].correct = random.random() < q
```

The `run` method first sorts the participants in `participants` in order from most starting money to least starting money. Then, for each participant who is not ranked first, it assigns the appropriate `next_participant` according to the `participants` list. Then, it calls `strategy` on every participant to set up `guess_threshold`, `prob_correct` etc. Then, it generates a random question easiness values based on the probability density function `Q` by taking the `Q`'s inverse CDF of a random number in the range $[0, 1]$. Then, for each participant, if the participant's `guess_threshold` is less than the generated question easiness value, the participant's `guess` field is set to `True`. Also if the participant's `guess_threshold` is less than the generated question easiness value, it generates a random number from $[0, 1]$ and sets the participant's `correct` field to `True` if the random number is less than the question easiness and `False` otherwise. After going through each participant in `participants`, the game is complete.

To create our 3D graphs, we wrote a program to write information from our simulated game to a spreadsheet and imported the spread sheet into the 3D graphing software *Graphing Calculator 3D*.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

Over the course of our research on the Tournament of Ten, we furthered our knowledge of continuous and discrete probability distributions and learned the basics of object-oriented programming, optimization methods via dynamic programming, and tools for 3D data visualization. We were able to code a simulation of the Tournament of Ten and create 3D graphs plotting varying values of m_1 and m_2 against $E'(P_2, Q(x))$ and analyze which question distributions maximized the expected profit of P_2 . We found from the data that for a majority of m_1 and m_2 values, the increasing question distribution gave the greatest values of $E'(P_2, Q(x))$.

In the future, we would like to use our simulation program to simulate games with different increasing question distributions to see if we can find an even more optimal distribution. For example, we could analyze the graphs of exponentially increasing or logarithmically increasing distribution functions and see if they yield better results than the increasing distribution given by $Q(x) = 2x$.

On another note, the Tournament of Ten offers various other mathematical pathways to explore. We also plan to analyze how different strategies affect the outcome of a tournament. Currently, all players in our simulated games employ the same strategy of guessing on a question whenever their expected profit of guessing is positive. We plan to examine what happens when a different strategy is used (for example, only guessing when the expected profit is greater than 0.5 times starting money) as well as what happens when strategies differ from player to player.

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